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Recommendations for effective partnerships

We need to move beyond collecting best-practices and move towards implementing policies and actions for a broad impact in food systems.

But how?

Establish fair and realistic representation in governance:

- Co-create a shared vision with input from all stakeholders
- Use understandable language and organise stakeholder visits to enable knowledge transfer and foster understanding among stakeholders
- Balance power structures that exist through knowledge, capacity and opportunity for advocacy, money- and funding flows

Work with data

- Provide reliable data (qualitative and quantitative) as the basis for discussion and ensure neutral facilitation between competing interests
- Non-conventional forms of experiential and indigenous knowledge can be a powerful lever and inspiration

Adapt funding and research priorities

- Ensure broad stakeholder consultation when identifying needs, challenges, and opportunities
- Enable place-based activities and enable adaptability for continuous learning
- Address the fact that food choices differ depending on social, technical and logistical infrastructure
- Encourage the development of interconnected networks regionally, nationally, and globally to address solutions along the entire supply chain.

Read the full report!

Curious to know more about these recommendations and the context behind them? Read the full report in our website!

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**FOODPathS:
Minimising
Trade-Offs and
maximizing
Co-benefits for
sustainable
food systems**

How can we ensure that the future of our food systems prioritizes health, safety, and taste while remaining sustainable?

How can we guarantee that all voices are heard and all actors are considered?

How can Research and Innovation shape effective solutions?

To tackle these challenges, a comprehensive, long-term strategy designed by different public, private, academic, philanthropic, and non-governmental stakeholders at local, regional, national, European and global levels is paramount.

In this context, the European Commission (EC) promotes the creation of **the European Partnership for Sustainable Food Systems (SFS) for People, Planet & Climate**, to be launched in 2024 (FutureFoodS).

Meaningful Stakeholder inclusion

We analysed best practices and interviewed experts to learn about roadblocks and opportunities for including meaningful input from diverse voices in Food Systems.

It appears that in European research we tend to communicate and act in particular ways and places, familiar to some and foreign to others.

To include more types of groups, we have to rethink our ways of communicating (methods, mediums, scales) and make language universally understandable and relevant.

What we learned:

1 A Shared Vision of Safe and Sustainable Food Systems is the basis for change. A shared vision helps articulate co-benefits and trade-offs can be easier to accept, since they act as means to an end.

3 There is no common definition of 'sustainable Food Systems', the term covers a broad range of topics and indicators. The EC works with a definition acknowledging both their essential value for people, planet and climate including e.g. biodiversity, social inclusion, income and EU's competitiveness.

2 Indicators for sustainability are closely related to the definition of a Sustainable Food Systems. Depending on the definition, different measurement units are used to describe impact and progress towards change.

4 How we design governance structures has a major impact on who benefits from decisions made and how to legitimize and elevate the needs and priorities of all food system stakeholders: it is important to consider who is, or is not, involved in the decision making process and to create systems to encourage inclusion and participation.

5 Methodologies for change vary widely. There are frameworks, tools, and techniques to put inclusiveness into practice. They can be data-informed guided discussions, bold visioning processes, policy development, action planning, or project implementation.

6 Needs and gaps in food systems – as well as the responsibility for change – lie along the whole supply chain, thus requiring solutions to react to different needs and stakeholders actions.